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Abstract

This paper investigates the factors promoting clean energy adoption by firms in the Middle East and North African (MENA) region as well as the internal and external factors moderating these effects. We propose a conceptual approach based on firms' knowledge and perception of clean technological possibilities organized into awareness, feasibility, and perceived efficiency. The main intuition is that implementation is the outcome of a careful cost-benefit evaluation in which firms gather information (awareness), assess technical viability (feasibility), and form expectations about profitability and efficiency gains (perceived efficiency). We empirically investigate if and to what extent these factors contribute to clean energy adoption and examine whether and how firms' participation in global value chains, the presence of female managers, and the existence of supportive government policies moderate these effects. Our results show that awareness is the key driver of implementing clean energy measures. Its effect is amplified for firms that are managed by females and for those that are part of global value chains. Yet, the awareness of government policies seems to be ineffective. Our results are robust to changes of independent variables, sample and estimation method.

Keywords: Clean energy, Global Value Chains, Firms, Middle East.

JEL: J16, O13, P18, Q49.

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1 Introduction

This paper investigates the factors promoting clean energy adoption by firms in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), with a focus on awareness, perceived feasibility and expected efficiency of these technologies. Advancing and accelerating the clean energy transition is not only a paramount global objective: it is becoming imperative for regions particularly vulnerable to climate change, especially developing areas. Facilitating firms' clean energy adoption requires balancing sufficiently stringent environmental regulations to spur innovation with concerns over possible short-run competitiveness costs (Porter & van der Linde, 1995; Copeland & Taylor, 2004). If policy makers have an incomplete, partial or misinformed understanding of the factors contributing to firms' implementation of environmentally friendly practices and clean energy adoption decisions, the risk is to delay the green transition, exposing the whole economy to greater socioeconomic costs in the future. This is especially true if policies and technologies are not well communicated to stakeholders and the general public, because firms will perceive them only as a cost. However, recent evidence shows that modern clean technologies should not undermine efficiency or competitiveness, and that well-designed environmental and innovation policies, reinforced by factors such as market competition and environmental preferences, can support economic performance while reducing environmental impacts (Aghion et al., 2016; Dechezleprêtre & Sato, 2017). Hence, exploring how firms' awareness and perception of clean technology in terms of feasibility and cost-efficiency shapes their adoption is fundamental in designing effective policies and fostering the transition.

The focus of this paper on the MENA countries adds to the relevance of the research because the region is among the most vulnerable to climate change and water stress (Lionello et al., 2014, UN, 2022 and Madani, 2026) and because advancing the transition is more urgent in developing economies where the trade-off between climate protection and competitiveness is perceived as more stringent. Furthermore, several MENA countries have adopted measures to mitigate climate change and accelerate the transition to a low-carbon economy, in line with the global framework established by the Paris Agreement (Sieghart and Betre, 2018). However, the firm-level energy transition in the MENA region is still largely underexplored.

Internal and external factors contributing to structural change and firms' implementation of climate-friendly practices and clean energy technology in emerging economies have not been thoroughly explored. This gap in the literature underscores the need to better understand how firms in the MENA context (but also more generally in developing regions), make decisions about clean energy adoption, and which factors facilitate or inhibit such decisions. Our paper contributes to this emerging agenda by focusing on firm-level perceptions and decision mechanisms, an area where quantitative analyses based on microdata remain scarce.

We investigate the factors driving clean energy adoption decisions among MENA firms proposing a conceptualization based on firms' knowledge and perception of clean technological possibilities organized into awareness, feasibility, and perceived efficiency. The main intuition is that implementation is the outcome of a careful cost-benefit evaluation in which firms gather information (awareness), assess technical viability (feasibility), and form expectations about profitability and efficiency gains (perceived efficiency). We then examine whether and how these three key drivers influence firms' clean energy adoption decisions.

The factors driving the cost-benefit evaluation leading to clean energy adoption (awareness, feasibility, and perceived efficiency), in turn, are likely to be moderated by internal and external factors. Among the external factors, regional integration in global value chains (GVCs) can contribute to the diffusion of environmentally friendly technologies. The MENA region's integration into GVCs is still modest and often limited to low value-added activities but thanks to its favorable geographical location, proximity to main markets, resource endowments, and abundant human capital, the region has potential for improvement (Ayadi et al., 2024). Moreover, government policies designed to spur firms' upgrading, as well as internal factors related to firms' organization and managerial practices, can also play an important role in the energy transition. Hence, we also examine whether and how firms' participation in GVCs, the existence of supportive government policies, and the presence of female managers contribute to clean energy adoption through firms' awareness regarding new technological opportunities, their perceived feasibility or expected efficiency.

Our main findings show that efficiency and feasibility positively affect the implementation of clean energy measures; and that awareness turns out to be the most important determinant. The effect is particularly pronounced for firms participating in

GVCs and firms with female managers. In contrast, government policies seem ineffective in moderating the impact of awareness, feasibility or efficiency on the implementation of energy transition measures. These results remain stable across different robustness checks for alternative samples, different measures and estimation methods.

This paper contributes to the literature on clean energy adoption by firms in developing economies in three main ways. First, it introduces a novel conceptual framework that organizes the determinants of adoption into three distinct drivers: awareness, feasibility, and perceived efficiency. While previous studies have already considered firm-level perceptions and objective constraints, they have typically treated these elements as aggregate or in isolation. By distinguishing these dimensions, we provide a more granular understanding of how firms internalize and act upon the energy transition agenda. Second, the paper empirically tests this framework using a unique, firm-level dataset covering four Middle Eastern and North African countries, namely Egypt, Jordan, Tunisia, and Morocco and provides a cross-country quantitative analysis of clean energy adoption in MENA firms. Third, the paper explores how the impact of awareness, feasibility, and efficiency on adoption is moderated by internal and external factors, such as participation in GVCs, the gender of the manager, and the presence of supportive government policies. These moderating effects help understand the economic conditions and the channels that make firms more likely to implement clean energy technologies, thus, having relevant policy implications.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature and explains the conceptual framework. Section 3 presents the data and main stylized facts. Section 4 discusses the research strategy, while section 5 provides the main results of our analysis. Finally, section 6 concludes and discusses policy implications.

2 Literature review and research hypotheses

The economics literature has identified a broad set of economic, market-related, contextual factors, as well as policy drivers and barriers to clean technology adoption. However, firm-level studies, especially those focusing on developing areas (and on the MENA region), remain scarce. Moreover, available studies often focus on single or narrowly defined channels, with limited attention to how firms form perceptions and

translate them into adoption decisions. Yet, the objective constraints identified in the literature also affect a firm's knowledge and perceptions of technological opportunities, an aspect that has been largely overlooked. Hence, little is known about how internal and external factors moderate firms' perceptions and, in turn, lead to adoption decisions. In particular, drivers and barriers have rarely been explicitly conceptualized as operating through firms' information constraints (awareness), perceived technical and organizational constraints (feasibility), and expectations about profitability or efficiency gains (efficiency), which form the organizing dimensions of our conceptual framework developed in Section 2.3. This paper seeks to fill these gaps by proposing and empirically testing a perception-based framework using firm-level data from MENA countries.

2.1 Clean energy adoption in developing countries

2.1.1 General trends and drivers of firm-level adoption

The global energy transition has accelerated over the past decade, but clean energy adoption remains uneven across regions, particularly in developing and emerging economies. In these contexts, firms often face financial constraints, institutional weaknesses, and information asymmetries that limit their ability to adopt sustainable technologies, while also shaping how adoption opportunities are perceived and evaluated at the firm level.

The existing literature highlights how cost savings, competitiveness and strategic positioning, as well as policy and financial incentives, may be important drivers of clean technology adoption. Expected or realized reductions in energy costs and increased energy savings are central motives moving manufacturing firms towards cleaner technologies (Hrovatin et al., 2021). Larger market share and export orientation (Hrovatin et al., 2016, for Slovenia), and participation in GVCs increase the probability of adopting cleaner and energy-saving practices, as firms face higher performance and environmental requirements from foreign buyers.⁴ Moreover, improved corporate image and alignment with long-term green industrial strategies can also motivate adoption, especially in more regulated or export-oriented environments (Usman et al., 2024).

⁴ Cf. Agostino et al., 2023, for both developed and developing countries, with the strongest GVC effects accruing to high-income countries.

These drivers operate not only through objective incentives, but also by shaping firms' expectations about the potential returns from clean technologies.

Government policies and institutional incentives – such as subsidies, favourable loans, tax breaks, and international agreements – may further support adoption by facilitating technology transfer and reducing adoption costs (Costantini and Liberati, 2014; Sun et al., 2019), thereby reinforcing both the perceived feasibility and expected efficiency of clean energy investments.

2.1.2 Barriers to adoption

High upfront investment costs, technological complexity, and the need for a skilled workforce for installation and maintenance are among the most frequently cited barriers (de Groot et al., 2001; Anderson and Newell, 2004). These barriers are often compounded by limited access to finance (Shi et al., 2025; Koirala, 2019; Tian and Lin, 2019; Zhindon-Almeida et al., 2025), obsolete technologies, limited infrastructure, and shortages of qualified human resources (Koirala, 2019; Karuppiah et al., 2020). Organizational and cultural barriers, including limited managerial knowledge and low awareness of potential benefits, further reduce firms' propensity to invest in clean energy (Jaffe and Stavins, 1994; de Groot et al., 2001; Usman et al., 2024). Moreover, less stringent environmental standards and weak or uncertain regulatory enforcement may further limit adoption (Ben-David et al., 2020; Ghosh and Dutta, 2022).

Importantly, many of these barriers can be interpreted as operating not only as objective constraints, but also through firms' limited awareness of technological options, perceived lack of technical feasibility, or uncertainty about expected efficiency and profitability gains. This insight motivates a perception-based approach to clean energy adoption, which complements existing constraint-based explanations by focusing on how firms process and evaluate these constraints when making adoption decisions.

2.2 Moderating factors

Beyond identifying drivers and barriers, the literature also points to internal and external factors that may condition how firms interpret and act upon these constraints. Some of

these factors may have a direct impact, as argued above, but they can also play an important moderating role by shaping how firms' perceptions translate into action. Building on the available literature, in the following, we focus on three dimensions – internal managerial characteristics, external production linkages, and government policies – that we believe are particularly relevant for shaping firms' perceptions and adoption decisions in developing-country contexts.

2.2.1 Internal factors

Firm-level characteristics and managerial practices play a central role in determining clean energy adoption decisions. Among these, gender dynamics in firm management have gained increasing attention in sustainability and energy literature as a potential source of heterogeneity in decision-making and information processing.

Gender is associated with differences in attitudes and responses to climate-related issues, with women more likely to express concern, while men tend to perceive material and psychological costs associated with mitigation as greater (Bush and Clayton, 2023). Evidence on intra-household's climate-related decisions aligns with this view, showing that households where women are more empowered regarding the choice of cooking fuel are more likely to adopt cleaner energy options such as gas or electricity (Chen et al., 2024). Although this evidence does not directly apply to manufacturing adoption decisions or firm-level investment choices, gender differences are likely to play a role in shaping the manager's and firm's attitudes towards clean energy.

At the same time, gender inequalities limit women's participation in the energy transition and advancement within the renewable energy sector (European Parliament, 2019). In the manufacturing sector in developing regions, women's participation is often concentrated in export-oriented, labor-intensive, low-tech activities (Mehra and Gammage, 1999 and Tejani and Milberg, 2016), with limited opportunities for skills upgrading and career progression. This structural concentration may constrain the scope for female managers to influence firms' awareness and evaluation of clean energy technologies, particularly in contexts characterized by rigid organizational hierarchies.

Some studies find that gender diversity in management is associated with greater adoption of sustainable practices, including energy efficiency measures (Dutta, 2020 and Opoku et al., 2021). Related firm-level evidence from developing regions shows that

female-managed firms can exhibit lower productivity, partly reflecting differential exposure to business constraints (Lo Bue and Martínez-Zarzoso, 2024). However, firm-level evidence on the role of female management in clean energy adoption remains limited, particularly in developing-country manufacturing and the MENA region, and little is known about whether and how gender moderates firms' perceptions regarding clean energy adoption.

2.2.2 External factors

Beyond government policies, external exposure through global production linkages represents another important channel affecting firms' clean energy adoption, particularly by shaping the informational and technological environments in which firms operate.

GVC participation is characterized by both ex-ante self-selection of more productive and innovative firms as well as by ex-post learning effects through knowledge spillovers (Eissa & Zaki, 2025; Ayadi et al., 2024; Urata & Baek, 2023; Benkovskis et al., 2020; Del Prete et al., 2017). While exporters and GVC firms tend to exhibit better environmental performance in developed economies (Richter & Schiersch, 2017; Holladay, 2016; Jinji & Sakamoto, 2015), aggregate effects remain ambiguous due to relocation of polluting activities – the so-called “Pollution Haven Hypothesis” (Antweiler et al., 2001; Copeland and Taylor, 2004; Duan et al., 2021). Conversely, recent evidence from African countries, based on country aggregate input-output data, suggests that GVC participation can support environmentally friendly structural transformation, consistently with the “Porter Hypothesis”, according to which well-designed environmental policies may stimulate innovation (Porter and van der Linde, 1995; Jaffe et al., 2002; Ali & Gnignue, 2021).

Within this literature, however, the microeconomic relationship between firms' GVC participation and clean energy adoption in emerging economies remains underexplored. Environmental regulations appear to foster GVC participation among MENA firms (Hazem and Zaki, 2025), while firms entering GVCs are more likely to adopt more efficient and environmentally friendly production technologies (Agostino et al., 2023; Siewers et al., 2024). This suggests a potentially reinforcing mechanism (and also a source of endogeneity) between environmental regulations, GVC participation, and clean energy adoption. More generally, evidence on how external exposure through GVCs and

policy environments shape firms' awareness, feasibility assessments, and expectations about returns from clean technologies remains scarce, particularly in the MENA region.

2.3 Conceptual framework and research hypotheses

A small but growing body of literature explores the determinants of clean energy adoption among firms in developing and middle-income countries. Yet, the mechanisms through which firms arrive at adoption decisions are still not fully understood. Much of the existing work implicitly treats firm attitudes as a single, undifferentiated construct, or separately focuses on external constraints (e.g., costs, regulations, market access). In contrast, we propose a conceptualization that distinguishes between three complementary dimensions: awareness, feasibility, and perceived efficiency. We define: i) *awareness* as a firm's knowledge and familiarity with clean energy technologies and their existence as viable options; ii) *feasibility* as the firm's internal perception of whether these technologies are understandable, operable, and compatible with existing processes or workforce skills; iii) *perceived efficiency* as the expected benefits from adopting clean energy solutions – such as cost savings, improved performance, or environmental improvements. This three-part framework reflects a cognitive-to-practical-to-economic logic. A firm must know about a solution (awareness), assess whether it can realistically implement it (feasibility), and consider whether it will pay off (efficiency). These aspects are conceptually distinct, and each can be a bottleneck.

Our conceptual diagram (Figure 1) presents these constructs as direct drivers of clean energy implementation, each represented as a testable hypothesis:

- **H1 (awareness):** Firms that are aware of green technologies are more likely to adopt them.
- **H2 (feasibility):** Firms that perceive green technologies as feasible are more likely to adopt them.
- **H3 (perceived efficiency):** Firms that expect efficiency gains from green technologies are more likely to adopt them.

We further hypothesize that the effects of these drivers are moderated by internal and external factors:

- **Internal factors**, such as the presence of female managers, may shape how information is interpreted and acted upon. We posit, for example, that awareness

may translate more effectively into implementation in female-led firms (*H1.int*), consistent with the view that managerial characteristics can affect how firms process information and respond to environmental challenges (Bush and Clayton, 2023; Chen et al., 2024).

- **External factors**, such as participation in GVCs or supportive government policies, may enhance awareness or the perceived feasibility or effectiveness of clean energy technologies. For instance, GVC participation may strengthen the link between awareness and adoption (*H1.ext*), while favorable policy environments may reinforce the link between feasibility and adoption (*H2.ext*).

Finally, external and internal factors may also exert direct effects on implementation, reflecting institutional pressure, access to knowledge networks, or organizational culture.

In what follows, we operationalize this framework using survey-based measures and test the direct association of awareness, feasibility and efficiency with adoption as well as their interaction with internal and external moderators.

Figure 1 – Conceptual diagram of possible effects of interest.

Note: solid lines represent direct effects; dashed lines represent moderating effects.
Source: authors' elaborations.

3 Data and Stylized Facts

3.1 MENA region: background and policy environment

The MENA region is among the most vulnerable to climate risks given its dependency on the primary sector and level of water stress.⁵ While oil-importing countries are dependent on agriculture that is sensitive to climate change, oil-exporting ones are highly dependent on oil that can turn into a stranded asset with stringent environmental laws. This is why most of MENA countries developed their own environmental and energy transition strategies and submitted a roadmap regarding their contributions established by the Paris Agreement.

Yet, when it comes to environmental regulations and treaties, the MENA region lags behind other developing and emerging regions. Hazem and Zaki (2025) show that, while Europe and Central Asia (ECA) have, on average, 642 environmental regulations per country and 78 environmental treaties adopted between 2006 and 2021, and Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) 623 have regulations and 45 treaties, the MENA region only has 150 regulations and 41 treaties. Furthermore, environmental treaties might not be effective in the MENA region given that they are weakly complemented by enforceable national regulations. Omojolaibi and Nathaniel (2020) show that the level of environmental regulations in the MENA region is still sub-optimal, which limits its effectiveness. Indeed, Abou Ali (2012) shows that, while several MENA countries created their ministries or other institutions overseeing environmental issues, the latter are still disconnected from other economic policies.

As per the energy transition, several strategies have been put in place by MENA countries. These can be classified into four main groups: macroeconomic measures, scaling-up renewable energy, green hydrogen initiatives, and enhancing energy efficiency. First, regarding macroeconomic measures, several MENA countries reduced their energy subsidies as part of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) stabilization reforms, e.g. Egypt and Jordan. Yet, it is important to distinguish between explicit and implicit subsidies. While explicit subsidies represent the difference between supply costs

⁵ See <https://www.wri.org/insights/highest-water-stressed-countries>. For every 1°C increase in average global temperature, UN experts predict a 20 percent decline in renewable water resources. Global warming is expected to increase the number of water-stressed areas and increase water stress in already affected regions

and retail prices and are directly paid by the government, implicit ones are the difference between the market price and the retail price (exclusive of any explicit subsidy). These implicit subsidies arise when government charges less than the true cost or gives preferential treatment to certain industries or sectors. MENA countries reduced their explicit subsidy, but their implicit one is still high because of price distortions that represent a significant obstacle to the acceleration of the decarbonization strategy (Eldeep et al., 2025). The IMF estimated that, in 2019, implicit energy subsidies in Egypt were five times higher than explicit subsidies, especially for diesel oil and gasoline. Second, several MENA countries are scaling-up their renewable energy, solar and wind energy. While fossil fuels generate more than 80% of the region's electricity, renewables are expected to dominate by 2040 until they reach 87% in 2060.⁶ Third, green hydrogen is currently becoming a growing strategic priority. This hydrogen is produced by splitting water into hydrogen and oxygen using renewable electricity through a process called electrolysis.⁷ Three countries are key players in this field, namely Saudi-Arabia, Egypt and Morocco. Saudi Arabia has large investments in the new city of NEOM that is projected to generate 600 tons of clean hydrogen per day. In the same vein, Egypt invests significantly in the Suez Canal Economic Zone and specifically in its infrastructure to become a regional hub and Morocco is on the way to establish a hydrogen market (Haytayan, 2025). Finally, several countries implemented energy efficiency measures such as using LEDs, installing light occupancy sensors, and energy audits, even though these measures are still impeded by vested interests in the fossil industry, deficient institutions and weak governance (Taghvaei et al., 2024).

3.2 Firm-level evidence

We use a novel and still unexploited firm-level dataset recently collected by the Economic Research Forum (ERF) covering four MENA countries (Egypt, Jordan, Tunisia, and Morocco). The data were collected in 2023 and cover micro, small and medium enterprises. The survey includes several modules specifying firms' characteristics and owner's characteristics as well as a module on energy transition. Our empirical sample

⁶ <https://www.dnv.com/energy-transition-outlook/2025/>

⁷ Generally, hydrogen can be classified into three main categories. Grey hydrogen is produced by splitting natural gas into hydrogen and CO₂, but the CO₂ is not being captured and is released into the atmosphere. Blue hydrogen is produced by splitting natural gas into hydrogen and CO₂, but the CO₂ is captured and then stored. Finally, green hydrogen is produced by splitting water by electrolysis.

includes the 791 firms operating in the manufacturing sector. After excluding observations with missing values in the key variables of interest, the regression sample consists of 757 firms (see Table A1 in the appendix for descriptive statistics).

The main outcome variable captures firms' engagement with clean energy transition measures. Specifically, the survey asks firms whether they have already implemented, or are currently considering implementing, measures related to clean or renewable energy use in their production processes. Based on the responses, we construct a binary indicator equal to one if the firm reports either having implemented or actively considering the implementation of clean energy measures, and zero otherwise. This definition allows us to capture firms that are at different stages of the adoption process, reflecting both realized implementation and near-term adoption intentions.⁸

Following the theoretical framework presented above, we focus on three determinants of implementing environmentally friendly measures, namely awareness, efficiency and feasibility. Using the survey, we construct a set of binary variables capturing respectively if the firm is aware of clean energy solutions or finds these measures feasible or perceives them as efficient. To do so, our first variable – *awareness* – takes the value of one if the owner is familiar with the term clean energy and with the term renewable energy, and zero otherwise (Gadenne et al., 2008). The second variable – *feasibility* – takes the value of one if the staff find renewable energy technologies easy to understand, if the installation and maintenance of renewable energy technology seem feasible and if the recommendations would encourage them to adopt renewable energy. The third dimension – *efficiency* – takes the value of one if the owner considers that the adoption of renewable energy technologies would improve the firm's energy efficiency, that the use of renewable energy technologies would enhance daily operations, and that renewable energy technologies would reduce energy costs⁹.

Table 1 shows the responses to each question and the measures we include in the empirical analysis. Overall, the share of firms that are aware of clean energy and renewable energy is around 59%. The shares of those who find them efficient and feasible

⁸ In robustness checks, we further restrict the sample by excluding firms that report having already implemented clean energy measures, in order to focus on adoption decisions among potential adopters. Results remain qualitatively unchanged under these alternative sample definitions.

⁹ Refer to Table A2 in the appendix that shows the correlation between these variables.

are lower, 54.1% and 40.2%, respectively. More heterogeneity is observed for individual variables. For awareness, more firms are aware of renewable energy (80.5%), agree that the latter can have a positive impact on the environment (81.3%), but much less agree that their installation and maintenance seem feasible (56.7%).

Generally, when the firm size is considered (see Figure 2), in line with our expectations, we find that micro firms are much less aware of energy efficiency measures, compared to their small and medium counterparts (65% vs. 51%). However, smaller differences are observed for the feasibility and for the efficiency perception (around 5 percentage points). These awareness differences might reflect disparities in their exposure to foreign technology and to trade that can affect their understanding and familiarity with energy transition concepts or differences in their innate characteristics.

In terms of innate characteristics, the gender of the manager seems to matter for awareness (see Figure 3). Overall, around 20% of firms are managed by females that are more educated compared to their male counterparts. The share of firms having a female manager are more likely to be aware than those with male managers, with 9 percentage points difference. In contrast, for efficiency and feasibility, no significant differences are observed between the two groups. This corroborates the literature on gender and climate change that shows that women are generally more sensitive to environmental issues and is in line with the gender socialization theory that argues that women are raised from childhood to be more compassionate and altruistic for others (Burkhardt et al., 2020).

Among the external determinants, internationalization is a key factor that can help firms adopt clean energy measures. As shown in Figure 4, we explore the different modes of internationalization, especially whether the firm is an exporter only, an importer only or a two-way trader (which we consider a proxy for being a GVC firm). Among the three modes, only GVC firms are significantly more aware of energy transition measures and perceive them more feasible. This shows to what extent both channels learning by exporting (Bernard and Jansen, 1999) and importing inputs (Bas and Berthou, 2017) can, on the one hand, make firms more exposed to such developments and become more aware, and on the other, become more productive and thus more likely to adopt these measures. This is in line with the results of Siewers et al. (2024) who argue that firms that enter GVCs perform better across different environmental measures such as environment-friendly production technologies and monitoring CO₂ emissions.

Figure 5 shows another external determinant related to the firms' awareness of government policies related to clean energy. Generally, all the firms that are aware of government policies are also more aware of clean energy measures and perceive the latter both feasible and efficient.

Table 1 – Energy efficiency indices

	No	Yes
Awareness (Yes to 1, 2)		
(1) Are you familiar with the term Clean Energy?	36.1	63.9
(2) Are you familiar with the term Renewable energy?	19.5	80.5
Efficiency (Yes to 3, 4, 5)		
(3) Adopting renewable energy technologies would improve our energy efficiency	27.2	72.8
(4) Use of renewable energy technologies would enhance our daily operations	31.5	68.5
(5) Renewable energy technologies would reduce our energy costs	22.7	77.3
Feasibility (Yes to 6, 7, 8)		
(6) Staff find renewable energy technologies easy to understand	40.0	60.0
(7) Installation and maintenance of renewable energy tech. seem feasible	43.3	56.7
(8) Recommendations would encourage us to adopt renewable energy	29.2	70.8

Note: (i) Yes and No refer to the firms' responses to each question.

(ii) Efficiency, Feasibility and Awareness are a binary variable that takes the value of one if all the responses to individual variables are yes and zero otherwise.

Source: authors' elaborations.

Figure 2 – Energy efficiency measures by firm size (%).

Note: (i) Numbers refer to the share of firms who respond yes to all the questions related to each dimension.

(ii) Micro firms have less than 5 employees. Small or medium between 5 and 100.

Source: authors' elaborations.

Figure 3 – Energy efficiency measures by the gender of the manager (%).

Note: Numbers refer to the share of firms who respond yes to all the questions related to each dimension.
Source: authors' elaborations.

Figure 4 – Energy efficiency measures by mode of internationalization (%).

Note: Numbers refer to the share of firms who respond yes to all the questions related to each dimension.
Source: authors' elaborations.

Figure 5 – Energy efficiency measures and government policies (%).

Note: Numbers refer to the share of firms who respond yes to this question “We're aware of government policies that support renewable energy technology adoption”.

Source: authors' elaborations.

4 Empirical strategy

In order to examine the determinants of implementing energy transition measures, we adopt the following specification:

$$Y_{isc} = \alpha + \beta X_{isc} + \gamma E_{isc} + \delta_s + \delta_c + \varepsilon_{isc} \quad (1)$$

Where Y measures whether the firm i in sector s in country c considers implementing energy transition measures. X is a vector of control variables that include firm age (measured as the difference between the year of establishment and the survey year) and firm size (a dummy variable that takes the value of one if the firm is micro and zero if small or medium). While older firms might have the means and the financial resources to implement such measures, younger firms might be more innovative and more likely to undertake environmental actions. E refers to the vector of our variables of interest, namely, awareness, feasibility and efficiency. These are three dummy variables that take the value 1 if the firm is aware of, perceives as feasible, or considers efficient the renewable and clean energy solutions, and 0 otherwise. Lastly, δ_s and δ_c are sector and country fixed effects to control for time-invariant unobservable factors, and ε_{isc} is the error term.

To test our hypotheses, we run the following specification:

$$Y_{isc} = \alpha + \beta X_{isc} + \gamma E_{isc} + \lambda F_{isc} + \sigma E_{isc} F_{isc} + \delta_s + \delta_c + \varepsilon_{isc} \quad (2)$$

Where F measures the internal and external factors that might moderate the impact of our determinants of interest E on the implementation of energy transition measures Y . Awareness, efficiency and feasibility are interacted sequentially with (i) the female manager dummy, (ii) the internationalization variables (dummies capturing whether the firm is a GVC firm or two-way trader, an importer only or an exporter only), and (iii) a government policy dummy indicating whether the owner is aware of any government policies related to energy transition. This will help us identify among the firms those that are aware of energy transition, find them efficient or feasible, and assess how the effect differs according to these three dimensions.

To test the robustness of our results, we proceed in three ways. First, we restrict the sample by removing the firms that have already implemented energy transition measures. This guarantees that our sample focuses exclusively on those who are considering implementation. Moreover, to reduce the reverse causation, we remove the top percentile of firms (based on size) which are more likely to have the financial and the human means to implement energy transition measures. Second, we change our main independent variables by using a principal component analysis to construct indices of efficiency, feasibility and awareness (instead of dummy variables). Finally, in terms of estimation methods, we run a propensity score matching where the treatment is whether the firm is aware of energy transition measures, and finds them feasible and efficient.

5 Results

5.1 Baseline results

Our baseline results are presented in Table 2. First, regarding our controls, while the age of the firm is not statistically significant, being a micro firm reduces the likelihood of considering implementing energy transition measures. This is in line with the literature that shows that micro firms are likely to be informal, with lower financial and technical

means, limited access to finance and thus innovating less, operating in sectors with limited value-added and thus less productive (Hendy and Zaki, 2013).

More importantly, energy transition variables are positive and statistically significant both when they are introduced individually (columns 1, 2 and 3) and together (column 4). Interestingly, when we look at the orders of magnitude of the estimates, awareness ranks first and its value remains stable when taken individually or with other variables, followed by efficiency and feasibility, the latter even reducing its statistical significance in the full model (column 4). These results indicate that firms' informational constraints – such as limited managerial knowledge and low awareness of potential benefits of investing in renewables – matter when it comes to the adoption of energy transition measures (de Groot et al., 2001; Usman et al., 2024).¹

Overall, our baseline results support our H1-H3 hypotheses, confirming that awareness, feasibility and perceived efficiency are among the determinants of clean energy adoption. However, these effects are likely to be moderated by several internal (gender of managers) and external (GVC participation and government policies) factors. The next section delves into these factors.

¹ Table A3 in the appendix show the individual regressions of each sub-index.

Table 2 – Baseline results.

Dep. var.: Implementation	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Awareness	0.141*** (0.0351)			0.141*** (0.0348)
Feasibility		0.104*** (0.0359)		0.0670* (0.0385)
Efficiency			0.117*** (0.0348)	0.0901** (0.0374)
Ln(age)	0.0273 (0.0231)	0.0224 (0.0239)	0.0234 (0.0235)	0.0273 (0.0231)
Micro	-0.0991** (0.0388)	-0.116*** (0.0394)	-0.117*** (0.0387)	-0.0948** (0.0388)
Constant	0.310*** (0.0741)	0.368*** (0.0744)	0.330*** (0.0749)	0.224*** (0.0772)
Observations	757	757	757	757
R-squared	0.075	0.066	0.069	0.094
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

5.2 External and internal moderating effects

As discussed above, gender can be considered an internal factor that moderates the impact of energy transition drivers on the likelihood of implementing different measures. Because gender is associated with differences in attitudes and responses to climate-related issues (Bush and Clayton, 2023), we expect that awareness may translate more effectively into implementation in female-led firms. The results on the moderating effect of female managers are presented in Table 3. First, the energy transition variables are consistent with our baseline specification. Second, gender per se does not seem to affect the likelihood of implementation as the female manager variable is either insignificant or significant at 10%. Third, and more importantly, when the gender variable is interacted with the energy transition ones, only awareness is positive and statistically significant, corroborating our initial predictions. This result is in line with those of Dibeh et al. (2021), Dutta (2020) and Opoku et al. (2021) who argue that gender diversity in management leads to an increase in the likelihood of adopting more sustainable measures. It is important to note that, in our sample, 13% of firms are managed by women. Most of these managers are better educated than their male counterparts. For

instance, while 43% of male managers have a university degree or higher, this share increases to 60% in the case of females.

Referring to our conceptual framework, the results from Table 3 support key moderating hypothesis *H1.int*, while the other possible channels (*H2.int* and *H3.int*) are not supported by the evidence.

Table 4 extends the previous results by focusing on the first external moderator, namely GVC participation. We introduce the GVC dummy variable and interact it with the energy transition ones. Moreover, for completeness, we also introduce two additional dummy variables, namely being an “importer only” or an “exporter only”². Several issues are worth mentioning. First, while the “exporter only” and “importer only” variables are not statistically significant – meaning that there is no difference with respect to domestic firms for what concerns clean energy adoption –, GVCs are positively correlated with the likelihood of considering implementing energy transition measures (column 1). Second, the interaction between GVC and the three energy-related variables yields interesting results. When they are interacted individually (columns 2-4), only the interaction between GVC and awareness is positive and statistically significant, with the coefficient of awareness itself positive and significant as well. This result is confirmed once all the interactions are introduced in the same regression (column 5), with the same level of significance and a similar numerical value of the estimates. Our findings support hypothesis *H1.ext* and confirm that both channels, learning by exporting and importing input, can make firms more exposed and become more aware of environmental challenges and thus more likely to adopt clean energy solutions (Siewers et al., 2024). This can also be potentially explained by the “Porter Hypothesis”, according to which stringent environmental policies may stimulate innovation (Porter and van der Linde, 1995).

Government policies are the second external factor that can moderate the impact of the energy transition variables on the likelihood of implementation. We expect that favorable policy environments may reinforce the link between feasibility and adoption (*H2.ext*). Yet, Table 5 shows that, while our baseline results are confirmed, neither the awareness of government policies alone nor its interactions with the three energy transition variables have significant effects on the likelihood of implementation. The insignificance

² As GVCs are proxied with two-way traders, the three internationalization dummies are mutually exclusive, while the reference group are domestic firms.

of the estimated effects is intriguing given that, despite the various measures, policies and regulations implemented in different MENA countries remain relatively ineffective. This result can be traced back to three main reasons. First, as mentioned before, environmental regulations remain below their optimal level (Omojolaibi and Nathaniel, 2020). Second, the implementation of energy efficiency measures is impeded by vested interests in the fossil industry, deficient institutions and weak governance (Taghvaei et al., 2024). Third, this result implies also that government campaigns and incentives are still not very developed.

Table 3 – Energy transition and gender.

Dep. var.: Implementation	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Awareness	0.137*** (0.0349)	0.110*** (0.0377)	0.137*** (0.0349)	0.137*** (0.0349)	0.109*** (0.0378)
Feasibility	0.0638* (0.0384)	0.0640* (0.0383)	0.0668 (0.0407)	0.0648* (0.0384)	0.0661 (0.0412)
Efficiency	0.0929** (0.0373)	0.0927** (0.0372)	0.0936** (0.0373)	0.0977** (0.0396)	0.0972** (0.0400)
Fem. Manager	0.110** (0.0551)	-0.0348 (0.0647)	0.121* (0.0651)	0.129* (0.0709)	-0.0134 (0.0764)
Awareness*Fem. Manager		0.217** (0.0877)			0.218** (0.0877)
Feasibility*Fem. Manager			-0.0252 (0.102)		-0.00975 (0.108)
Efficiency*Fem. Manager				-0.0385 (0.0978)	-0.0350 (0.104)
Ln(age)	0.0323 (0.0233)	0.0299 (0.0233)	0.0325 (0.0233)	0.0328 (0.0233)	0.0304 (0.0233)
Micro	-0.101*** (0.0387)	-0.0989** (0.0384)	-0.101*** (0.0387)	-0.100*** (0.0387)	-0.0985** (0.0385)
Constant	0.205*** (0.0775)	0.227*** (0.0781)	0.203*** (0.0779)	0.201** (0.0781)	0.222*** (0.0788)
Observations	757	757	757	757	757
R-squared	0.099	0.105	0.099	0.099	0.105
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 4 – Energy transition and internationalization.

Dep. var.: Implementation	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Awareness	0.138*** (0.0348)	0.112*** (0.0360)	0.138*** (0.0348)	0.139*** (0.0348)	0.112*** (0.0360)
Feasibility	0.0621 (0.0385)	0.0628 (0.0384)	0.0690* (0.0397)	0.0637* (0.0384)	0.0637 (0.0399)
Efficiency	0.0917** (0.0372)	0.0872** (0.0371)	0.0922** (0.0373)	0.106*** (0.0382)	0.106*** (0.0384)
Importer only	0.00364 (0.0365)	0.00500 (0.0365)	0.00344 (0.0365)	0.00307 (0.0365)	0.00444 (0.0365)
Exporter only	-0.0762 (0.0839)	-0.0779 (0.0839)	-0.0762 (0.0839)	-0.0757 (0.0840)	-0.0774 (0.0841)
GVC	0.179** (0.0694)	-0.0516 (0.0950)	0.219** (0.0910)	0.275*** (0.0947)	0.0445 (0.107)
Awareness*GVC		0.350*** (0.124)			0.382*** (0.121)
Feasibility*GVC			-0.0889 (0.133)		0.0146 (0.143)
Efficiency*GVC				-0.189 (0.128)	-0.242* (0.142)
Ln(age)	0.0334 (0.0228)	0.0353 (0.0226)	0.0333 (0.0228)	0.0341 (0.0227)	0.0364 (0.0225)
Micro	-0.0898** (0.0389)	-0.0863** (0.0389)	-0.0905** (0.0390)	-0.0908** (0.0388)	-0.0871** (0.0387)
Constant	0.202** (0.0784)	0.211*** (0.0785)	0.199** (0.0786)	0.191** (0.0782)	0.198** (0.0783)
Observations	757	757	757	757	757
R-squared	0.105	0.114	0.106	0.108	0.119
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 5 – Energy transition and government policies.

Dep. var.: Implementation	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Awareness	0.139*** (0.0349)	0.142*** (0.0456)	0.139*** (0.0349)	0.140*** (0.0348)	0.143*** (0.0457)
Feasibility	0.0597 (0.0400)	0.0597 (0.0401)	0.0828 (0.0582)	0.0598 (0.0401)	0.0887 (0.0607)
Efficiency	0.0856** (0.0378)	0.0855** (0.0377)	0.0840** (0.0379)	0.0820 (0.0498)	0.0712 (0.0521)
Awar. Gov. Pol.	0.0324 (0.0377)	0.0359 (0.0526)	0.0488 (0.0478)	0.0283 (0.0532)	0.0424 (0.0645)
Awareness*Awar. Gov. Pol.		-0.00573 (0.0689)			-0.00632 (0.0688)
Feasibility*Awar. Gov. Pol.			-0.0410 (0.0766)		-0.0509 (0.0813)
Efficiency*Awar. Gov. Pol.				0.00753 (0.0717)	0.0257 (0.0759)
Ln(age)	0.0271 (0.0232)	0.0272 (0.0232)	0.0270 (0.0232)	0.0271 (0.0232)	0.0269 (0.0233)
Micro	-0.0918** (0.0391)	-0.0916** (0.0392)	-0.0915** (0.0392)	-0.0916** (0.0391)	-0.0906** (0.0392)
Constant	0.214*** (0.0779)	0.213*** (0.0796)	0.209*** (0.0785)	0.216*** (0.0800)	0.212*** (0.0813)
Observations	757	757	757	757	757
R-squared	0.095	0.095	0.095	0.095	0.096
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

5.3 Robustness checks

We test the robustness of our results in several ways (see Table 6).

First, we restrict the sample by removing the firms that have already implemented energy transition measures to guarantee that our sample focuses exclusively on those who consider implementation: our baseline results are confirmed (column 1).

Second, instead of directly combining survey answers into binary variables to measure a firm's energy transition perceptions, we use a principal component analysis to construct the indices of efficiency, feasibility and awareness. The advantage of this methodology is that it endogenously generates the weights attributed to each component and then the main latent components that explain the largest share of the common variation among these variables are extracted. Again, awareness turns out to be the most important determinant (column 2). The only difference pertains to the significance of feasibility.

Third, to reduce the reverse causation, we remove the top percentile of firms (based on size) as larger firms are more likely to have the financial and the human means to implement energy transition measures. Column (3) confirms all the results of the baseline.

Lastly, in terms of the estimation method, we run a propensity score matching where the treatment is whether the firm is aware of energy transition measures or finds them feasible and efficient. Figure 6 shows that the treatment has positive and statistically significant effects, with awareness, followed by efficiency then feasibility being the key drivers of implementation. In terms of balancing and matching characteristics, Figure A1 in the appendix shows also that comparable firms exist in the treatment and control groups with a large common support region. Moreover, Table A4 shows that there are no systematic differences between the characteristics of treated and untreated firms.

Table 6 – Alternative measures.

Dep. var.: Implementation	Without already implemented	PCA indices	Without top 1% by size
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Awareness	0.135*** (0.0349)	0.137*** (0.0226)	0.105*** (0.0372)
Feasibility	0.0686* (0.0389)	0.0829*** (0.0259)	0.0612 (0.0409)
Efficiency	0.0823** (0.0376)	0.0300 (0.0239)	0.0911** (0.0395)
Ln(age)	0.0228 (0.0233)	0.0235 (0.0230)	0.0176 (0.0244)
Micro	-0.0858** (0.0394)	-0.0768** (0.0385)	-0.0883** (0.0413)
Observations	737	757	670
R-squared	0.081	0.114	0.083
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: column 1 removes the firms that have already implemented energy transition measures. Column 2 uses a principal component analysis to construct the indices of efficiency, feasibility and awareness. Column 3 removes the top percentile of firms (based on size) as the latter are more likely to have the financial and the human means to implement energy transition measures.

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Figure 6 – Alternative estimation methods.

Note: Each line represents a regression where each treatment (awareness, efficiency, and feasibility) is introduced individually. “All” refers to the case where all the treatments are equal to one and “One” refers to the case where any of the three treatments is equal to one.

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

6 Conclusion

This paper investigates the determinants of clean energy adoption among MENA firms using a perception-based approach that complements existing constraint-based explanations. Our analysis focuses on how firms process available information and evaluate perceived constraints when making clean energy adoption decisions (where adoption captures either having implemented or actively considering implementation). The main intuition is that adoption is the outcome of a careful cost-benefit evaluation in which firms gather information, assess technical viability, and form expectations about profitability and efficiency gains. A key contribution is to explicitly conceptualize drivers and barriers as operating partly through firms' perceptions of clean-technology options structured around awareness, perceived feasibility, and expected efficiency.

We provide new empirical evidence consistent with this framework. The main findings indicate that awareness, efficiency and feasibility are positively associated with clean energy adoption. Awareness emerges as the most important determinant, with the largest significant marginal effect in the baseline specification. Two factors strengthen the awareness-adoption link: female management (an internal factor) and GVC participation (an external factor). In contrast, awareness of government policies does not turn out to be statistically significant and does not robustly moderate the roles of awareness, feasibility, or efficiency.

The positive association of firms' awareness, perceived feasibility, and expected efficiency with clean energy adoption suggests that, while removing objective constraints and barriers to adoption remains the key policy objective, enhancing firms' knowledge and perceptions of clean energy solutions through effective communication and human capital formation is also important. Crucially, even policies that are successful at reducing objective constraints (e.g., removing financial barriers, helping with the high upfront investments, addressing limited infrastructure) may have weaker or delayed effectiveness if they do not also improve awareness among managers, workers, and firms. This suggests that while devising policies is necessary, how they are implemented and perceived by possible beneficiaries also play a relevant role.

Our results on the moderating channels also spur relevant considerations. Considering the internal factors, managerial gender diversity can bring varied, complementary

environmental sensitivities and skills within the firm, increasing openness to clean energy solutions. Policies favouring female participation in management may strengthen how awareness translates into adoption. Regarding the external factors, GVC participation often involves exchanges of information and best practices between firms. Policies that foster deeper integration into GVCs and, specifically, collaboration with other firms, could facilitate clean energy adoption, potentially by improving firms' knowledge and perceptions regarding possible technological solutions. In contrast, the finding that awareness of government policies does not appear to play a relevant role is concerning but also informative. This may reflect limited salience, communication, or credibility of policy instruments for firms. It also suggests a possible need to reinforce transparency and trust around existing policies, and to work towards a more effective implementation. This is particularly important in the MENA region, considering that it has comparatively fewer clean energy regulations and treaties than other regions, and that they are weakly complemented by enforceable national regulations, which limits effectiveness.

Overall, this paper proposes a new approach that complements existing studies addressing drivers and barriers of clean energy adoption, pointing out the relevance of improving firms' knowledge and perceptions regarding available technological options. While our results are robust to alternative measures of key variables, sample compositions and estimation methods, some limitations remain. One main limitation is due to data availability and the cross-sectional nature of the analysis, which limits causal interpretations and raises potential endogeneity concerns. Another limitation regards the difficulties in measuring qualitative constructs such as awareness, perceived feasibility, and expected efficiency. Moreover, as perceptions and adoption are self-reported within the same survey, common-method bias and unobserved managerial traits may inflate correlations; robustness checks help, but they do not fully resolve these concerns. While the ERF survey contains new useful information and questions that allowed us to construct reasonable proxies, more and better data are needed to advance the analysis in the directions suggested by our approach. Our work may stimulate future research using panel data and developing better perception-based indicators.

References

- Aghion, P., Dechezleprêtre, A., Hémous, D., Martin, R., & Van Reenen, J. (2016). Carbon Taxes, Path Dependency, and Directed Technical Change: Evidence from the Auto Industry. *Journal of Political Economy*, 124(1), 1–51. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26549857>
- Agostino, M., Giunta, A., Ruberto, S., & Scalera, D. (2023). Global value chains and energy-related sustainable practices. Evidence from Enterprise Survey data. *Energy Economics*.
- Ali, E., & Gninigue, M. (2022). Global value chains participation and structural transformation in Africa: Are we advocating environmental protection?. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 366, 132914.
- Anderson, S. T., & Newell, R. G. (2004). Information programs for technology adoption: the case of energy-efficiency audits. *Resource and Energy Economics*, 26(1), 27–50.
- Antweiler, Werner; Brian R. Copeland and M. Scott Taylor (2001). “Is Free Trade Good for the Environment?” *Amer. Econ. Rev.* 91:4, pp. 877–908.
- Ayadi, R., Giovannetti, G., Marvasi, E., & Zaki, C. (2024). Trade networks and the productivity of MENA firms in global value chains. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 69, 10–23.
- Ayadi, R., Giovannetti, G., Marvasi, E., Vannelli, G., & Zaki, C. (2021). Demand and Supply Exposure through Global Value Chains: Euro-Mediterranean Countries during COVID. *The World Economy*, twec.13156. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.13156>
- Baek, Y., & Urata, S. (2023). Does global value chain participation improve firm productivity? A study of selected ASEAN developing countries. *Asian Economic Journal*, 37(2), 232–260.
- Bas, M., & Berthou, A. (2017). Does input-trade liberalization affect firms’ foreign technology choice?. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 31(2), 351–384.
- Ben-David, I., Kleimeier, S., Viehs, M., 2020. When environmental regulations are tighter at home, companies emit more abroad: there should be no haven for pollution. In: *Climate Change: The Insights You Need from Harvard Business Review*. Harvard Business Review Press, pp. 43–51. HBR Insights Series.
- Benkovskis, K., Masso, J., Tkacevs, O., Vahter, P., & Yashiro, N. (2020). Export and productivity in global value chains: Comparative evidence from Latvia and Estonia. *Review of World Economics*, 156(3), 557–577.
- Bernard, A. B., & Jensen, J. B. (1999). Exceptional exporter performance: cause, effect, or both?. *Journal of international economics*, 47(1), 1–25.
- Burkhardt, K., Nguyen, P., & Poincelot, E. (2020). Agents of change: Women in top management and corporate environmental performance. *Corporate social responsibility and environmental management*, 27(4), 1591–1604.
- Bush, S. S., & Clayton, A. (2023). Facing change: Gender and climate change attitudes worldwide. *American Political Science Review*, 117(2), 591–608.
- Cagno, E., Worrell, E., Trianni, A., Pugliese, G., 2013. A novel approach for barriers to industrial energy efficiency. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 19, 290–308.
- Chen, J., Liao, H., & Zhang, T. (2024). Empowering women substantially accelerates the household clean energy transition in China. *Energy Policy*, 187, 114048.
- Copeland, Brian R., and M. Scott Taylor (2004). Trade, Growth, and the Environment. *Journal of Economic Literature* 42 (1): 7–71.
- De Groot, H. L., Verhoef, E. T., & Nijkamp, P. (2001). Energy saving by firms: decision-making, barriers and policies. *Energy Economics*, 23(6), 717–740.
- Dechezleprêtre, A., & Sato, M. (2017). The Impacts of Environmental Regulations on Competitiveness. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 11, 183 - 206.

- Del Prete D, Giovannetti G, Marvasi E (2017) Global Value Chains Participation and Productivity Gains for North African Firms. *Review of World Economics*, Springer.
- Dibeh, G., Fakhri, A., Marrouch, W., & Matar, G. (2021). Who cares about environmental quality in the MENA region?. *Social Indicators Research*, 157(2), 603-629.
- Duan, Y., Ji, T., & Yu, T. (2021). Reassessing pollution haven effect in global value chains. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 284, 124705.
- Dutta, S. Powering Equality: Women's Entrepreneurship Transforming Asia's Energy Sector.
- Eissa, Y., & Zaki, C. (2025). Leveraging global value chains for innovation: the case of SMEs. *International Economics*, 100599.
- Gadenne, D. L., Kennedy, J., & McKeiver, C. (2009). An empirical study of environmental awareness and practices in SMEs. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 84(1), 45-63.
- Ghosh, D., Dutta, M., 2022. Environmental behaviour under credit constraints – evidence from panel of Indian manufacturing firms. *Struct. Chang. Econ.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strueco.2022.07.004>.
- Haytayan, L. (2025) The Energy Dilemma Energy Transition and Regional Collaboration in the Middle East and North Africa, Natural Resources Governance Institute.
- Hazem, N., & Zaki, C. (2025). Environmental Stringency and Firms' Participation in Global Value Chains: Evidence for MENA Countries (No. 11161). The World Bank.
- Holladay, J. S. (2016). Exporters and the environment. *Canadian Journal of Economics/Revue canadienne d'économique*, 49(1), 147-172.
- Hrovatin, N., Cagno, E., Dolšak, J., & Zorić, J. (2021). How important are perceived barriers and drivers versus other contextual factors for the adoption of energy efficiency measures: An empirical investigation in manufacturing SMEs. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.
- Hrovatin, N., Dolšak, N., & Zorić, J. (2016). Factors impacting investments in energy efficiency and clean technologies: empirical evidence from Slovenian manufacturing firms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 127, 475-486.
- Jaffe, A. B., & Stavins, R. N. (1994). The energy-efficiency gap What does it mean?. *Energy policy*, 22(10), 804-810.
- Jaffe, A. B., Newell, R. G., & Stavins, R. N. (2002). Environmental policy and technological change. *Environmental and resource economics*, 22(1), 41-70.
- Jinji, N., & Sakamoto, H. (2015). Does exporting improve firms' CO2 emissions intensity and energy intensity? Evidence from Japanese manufacturing. Research Institute for Economy, Trade and Industry Discussion Paper, 1-27.
- Karuppiah, K., Sankaranarayanan, B., Ali, S., Chowdhury, P., & Paul, S. (2020). An integrated approach to modeling the barriers in implementing green manufacturing practices in SMEs. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 265, 121737.
- Koirala, S., 2019. SMEs: Key Drivers of Green and Inclusive Growth, OECD Green Growth Papers, 2019–03. OECD Publishing, Paris. Retrieved July 30, 2022 from. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/environment/smes-key-drivers-of-green-and-inclusive-growth_8a51fc0c-en.
- Lionello, P., Abrantes, F., Gacic, M., Planton, S., Trigo, R., & Ulbrich, U. (2014). The climate of the Mediterranean region: research progress and climate change impacts. *Regional Environmental Change*, 14(5), 1679-1684.
- LoBue, M. C., & Martínez-Zarzoso, I. (2024). Female managers and firm performance: Evidence from the non-agricultural sectors in caribbean countries. *Economic Modelling*, 133, 106648.
- Madani K. (2026) Global Water Bankruptcy: Living Beyond Our Hydrological Means in the Post-Crisis Era, United Nations University Institute for Water, Environment and Health (UNU-INWEH), Richmond Hill, Ontario, Canada, doi: 10.53328/INR26KAM001

- Mehra, R., & Gammage, S. (1999). Trends, countertrends, and gaps in women's employment. *World Development*, 27(3), 533-550.
- Opoku, E. E. O., Kufuor, N. K., & Manu, S. A. (2021). Gender, electricity access, renewable energy consumption and energy efficiency. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 173, 121121.
- Peng, X., & Liu, Y. (2016). Behind eco-innovation: Managerial environmental awareness and external resource acquisition. *Journal of cleaner production*, 139, 347-360.
- Porter, M., & van der Linde, C. (1995). Green and Competitive: Ending the Stalemate. Chapters, in: Emiel F.M. Wubben (ed.), *The Dynamics of the Eco-Efficient Economy*, chapter 2, pages 33-56, Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Richter, P. M., & Schiersch, A. (2017). CO2 emission intensity and exporting: Evidence from firm-level data. *European Economic Review*, 98, 373-391.
- Rustam, A., Wang, Y., & Zameer, H. (2020). Environmental awareness, firm sustainability exposure and green consumption behaviors. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 268, 122016.
- Shi, Z., Li, B., & Bilti, R. (2025). Constraints to sustainable energy technology implementation: Insights from an emerging economy using ISM-MICMAC analysis. *PLOS One*, 20.
- Sieghart, L. C., & Betre, M. (2018). Climate change in MENA: challenges and opportunities for the world's most water stressed region. *MENA Knowledge and Learning*, 164.
- Siewers, S., Martínez-Zarzoso, I., & Baghdadi, L. (2024). Global value chains and firms' environmental performance. *World Development*, 173, 106395.
- Sorrell, S., Schleich, J., Scott, S., O'Malley, E., Trace, F., Boede, U., Ostertag, K., Radgen, P., 2000. Reducing Barriers to Energy Efficiency in Public and Private Organizations. Science and Policy Technology Research (SPRU), University of Sussex, Sussex, UK.
- Taghvaei, V. M., Saboori, B., Soretz, S., Magazzino, C., & Tatar, M. (2024). Renewable energy, energy efficiency, and economic complexity in the middle East and North Africa: A panel data analysis. *Energy*, 311, 133300.
- Tejani, S., & Milberg, W. (2016). Global defeminization? Industrial upgrading and manufacturing employment in developing countries. *Feminist Economics*, 22(2), 24-54.
- Tian, P., Lin, B., 2019. Impact of financing constraints on firm's environmental performance: evidence from China with survey data. *J. Clean. Prod.* 217 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.01.209>.
- UN World Water Development Report 2022: Groundwater: Making the invisible visible.
- Usman, F., Ani, E., Ebirim, W., Montero, D., Olu-Lawal, K., & Nindwezuor-Ehiobu, N. (2024). INTEGRATING RENEWABLE ENERGY SOLUTIONS IN THE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES: A REVIEW. *Engineering Science & Technology Journal*.
- Zhindaon-Almeida, R., & Ruiz-Carrillo, J. (2025). Factors Influencing the Adoption of Renewable Energies in Developing Countries. *Sustainable Development*.

Appendix

Table A1. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Ln(Age)	757	2.35	0.78	0.69	5.41
Micro	791	0.43	0.50	0	1
Awareness	791	0.60	0.49	0	1
Efficiency	791	0.55	0.50	0	1
Feasibility	791	0.39	0.49	0	1
Fem. Manager	791	0.13	0.34	0	1
Exporter only	791	0.04	0.21	0	1
Importer only	791	0.43	0.50	0	1
GVC	791	0.09	0.28	0	1
Awar. Gov. Pol.	791	0.49	0.50	0	1
Imp.	791	0.36	0.48	0	1

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Table A2. Correlation Matrix

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
(1)	1.00										
(2)	0.50 (0.00)	1.00									
(3)	0.32 (0.00)	0.33 (0.00)	1.00								
(4)	0.23 (0.00)	0.28 (0.00)	0.32 (0.00)	1.00							
(5)	0.22 (0.00)	0.26 (0.00)	0.26 (0.00)	0.41 (0.00)	1.00						
(6)	0.33 (0.00)	0.31 (0.00)	0.29 (0.00)	0.32 (0.00)	0.33 (0.00)	1.00					
(7)	0.07 (0.00)	0.05 (0.01)	0.01 (0.51)	0.04 (0.03)	0.02 (0.30)	0.03 (0.07)	1.00				
(8)	0.19 (0.00)	0.12 (0.00)	0.09 (0.00)	0.07 (0.00)	0.04 (0.01)	0.10 (0.00)	0.44 (0.00)	1.00			
(9)	0.10 (0.00)	0.06 (0.00)	0.02 (0.31)	0.03 (0.07)	0.02 (0.35)	0.04 (0.03)	0.92 (0.00)	0.60 (0.00)	1.00		
(10)	0.64 (0.00)	0.69 (0.00)	0.62 (0.00)	0.33 (0.00)	0.29 (0.00)	0.32 (0.00)	0.04 (0.02)	0.11 (0.00)	0.05 (0.00)	1.00	
(11)	0.22 (0.00)	0.29 (0.00)	0.29 (0.00)	0.64 (0.00)	0.71 (0.00)	0.49 (0.00)	0.02 (0.20)	0.04 (0.02)	0.01 (0.40)	0.35 (0.00)	1.00

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Notes: p-value between brackets. (1) Adopting renewable energy technologies would improve our energy efficiency. (2) The use of renewable energy technologies would enhance our daily operations. (3) Renewable energy technologies would reduce our energy costs. (4) Our staff finds renewable energy technologies easy to understand and operate. (5) The installation and maintenance of renewable energy technology seem hassle-free. (6) Recommendations would encourage us to adopt renewable energy technologies. (7) Are you familiar with the term Clean Energy. (8) Are you familiar with the term Renewable energy? (9) Awareness. (10) Efficiency. (11) Feasibility.

Table A3. Results of Individual Measures (dep. var.: implementation)

Model	Main variable of interest	
Awareness		
(1)	Are you familiar with the term Clean Energy?	0.155*** (0.0346)
(2)	Are you familiar with the term Renewable energy?	0.209*** (0.0385)
Feasibility		
(3)	Staff find renewable energy technologies easy to understand	0.138*** (0.0347)
(4)	Installation and maintenance of renewable energy techn. seem	0.114*** (0.0343)
(5)	Recommendations would encourage us to adopt renewable energy	0.0968** (0.0375)
Efficiency		
(6)	Adopting renewable energy technologies would improve our energy efficiency	0.129*** (0.0375)
(7)	Use of renewable energy technologies would enhance our daily operations	0.103*** (0.0370)
(8)	Renewable energy technologies would reduce our energy costs	0.106*** (0.0400)
Models information		
	Observations	757
	Country dummies	Yes
	Sector dummies	Yes

Robust standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1
Each line represents a regression where all the controls are included.

Figure A.1. Propensity score histogram by treatment status.

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Table A.4. Covariate imbalance testing with baseline variables

	Mean		p> t
	Treated	Control	
Ln(age)	2.248	2.252	0.909
Micro	0.456	0.467	0.601
Sec. dum 1	0.040	0.042	0.777
Sec. dum 2	0.033	0.034	0.900
Sec. dum 3	0.089	0.089	0.975
Sec. dum 4	0.038	0.042	0.632
Sec. dum 5	0.036	0.033	0.717
Sec. dum 6	0.049	0.047	0.824
Sec. dum 7	0.261	0.270	0.628
Sec. dum 8	0.086	0.079	0.554
Sec. dum 9	0.017	0.017	0.982
Sec. dum 10	0.058	0.057	0.969
Sec. dum 11	0.046	0.045	0.885
Sec. dum 12	0.054	0.055	0.880
Sec. dum 13	0.116	0.114	0.883
Sec. dum 14	0.054	0.055	0.952
Country dum. 1	0.402	0.382	0.343
Country dum. 3	0.274	0.278	0.847

Source: Authors' own elaboration.